

PART 1 Archiving Wizard - Active Projects

This form will help take you through the steps to archive your digital work.

It will facilitate three different tasks. These are:

- I. registering your project and establishing copyright clearance;
- II. creating 3 citable project documentation products including:
 - 1. a catalogue record,
 - 2. a persistent identifier, and
 - 3. an Archiving Dossier Narrative (Active); and
- III. storing project information not intended for citation.

After completing the form, you may begin to [self-archive](#), or, an institutional cataloguer will contact you to confirm what you have entered. You will then need to complete [PART 2 of the Archiving Dossier Wizard for Active Projects \(the DARK GREEN form\)](#). Please be as thorough as possible. The more information you provide, the easier it will be for scholars to find and cite your digital work.

Email

repositorioconcepcioncabrera@g
mail.com

**Are you working with a
cataloguer at your institution to
archive your digital project?**
 Yes No

**Please provide the email of the
cataloguer at your institution.**

I. Project Registration and Copyright Clearance

This section will allow project participants to officially start the archiving process and set rights to usage.

Website

https://sites.google.com/view/concepcioncabrera1

Please provide an address (url) where the project is currently located.

Please list project participants and their current email addresses.

Rodolfo Saúl Ibarra Robles
saulibarra1@gmail.com

Is this project sponsored by an organization? If so, name the organization.

Misioneros del Espíritu Santo

Copyright Clearance Statement

"I hereby certify that the submission described in this document abides by the principles stipulated in the Memorandum of Understanding/Deposit Agreement concluded between project archivers and the digital repository. I further certify that all intellectual property and any images reproduced in this submission are cleared of copyright and have been properly cited."

Do you and all project contributors agree to license this work under a creative common license?

Yes No

(<https://creativecommons.org/choose/>)

Which creative common's license did you choose for your project?

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Have signed a MOU (memo of understanding) with your digital repository?

Yes No

II.1. Creating Citable Project Documentation: The catalogue record

Uses Dublin Core Metadata Element Set. 1.1

Title: What is the title of the digital project?

Repositorio Digital Concepción Cabrera

Subject: Identify the related subjects of the project.

Patrimonio Cultural; Manuscritos originales; Escritora; Mujer mexicana

Use keywords, key phrases, or classification codes. LOC classification outline:

<https://www.loc.gov/catdir/cpsol/lcco/>

Description: Describe your digital resource

Es un repositorio que contiene los manuscritos más importantantes digitalizados de la obra de Concepción Cabrera

May include but is not limited to: an abstract, a table of contents, a graphical representation, or a free-text account of the resource.

Creator(s): Name the entity(es) primarily responsible for making the resource

Rodolfo Saúl Ibarra Robles

If multiple authors/creators exist, please separate each by semicolon.

Publisher: What entity was responsible for making the resource available?

INSTITUTO TECNOLÓGICO DE ESTUDIOS SUPERIORES DE MONTERREY

Contributor: List all contributors to this project

Please separate entries by semicolon.

Format: What file formats are used in the project?

PDF
TXT
JPG

User Interface: What user interface was used in the project?

WordPress 4.9.8

Please give version used (eg. Omeka 2.0, WordPress 4.9.8, etc.)

Language: What language or languages is the project written in?

Spa

Type: What is the nature or genre of the resource?

Web resource

Web resource, searchable database, visualization, eg.

Start Date: What date marks the beginning of project?

23/01/2021

Launch Date: When was the project publicly launched?

21/11/2021

Would you like to permanently archive this project?

Yes No

If the answer is "yes," please give Archiving Date.

30/11/2021

Cataloguing/Archiving Digital Text Initiatives.

Yes No

Do you know how to convert your HTML (web) pages to a PDF format?

Are you self archiving?

Yes No

Try these strategies

Choose the "pdf" option on your printer. Read this wiki: <https://www.wikihow.com/Convert-a-Webpage-to-PDF>

Cataloguing and Archiving Site Content 1 (PDFs)

Using the buttons below, upload your project webpages in PDF format, one PDF per webpage.

Do you have between 1-20 pdf files to upload?

www.concepcioncabrera.com - Blog.pdf

www.concepcioncabrera.com - Videos.pdf

www.concepcioncabrera.com - Autobiografía.pdf

www.concepcioncabrera.com - Psicología.pdf

www.concepcioncabrera.com - Historia.pdf

www.concepcioncabrera.com - Recursos.pdf

www.concepcioncabrera.com - PODCAST.pdf

www.concepcioncabrera.com - Manuscritos originales.pdf

www.concepcioncabrera.com - Cuenta de Conciencia.pdf

www.concepcioncabrera.com - Descargar Vida.pdf

1. Inicio.pdf

www.concepcioncabrera.com - Frases.pdf

www.concepcioncabrera.com - Retiros Espirituales.pdf

Do you have more than 21 pdf files to upload?

Yes No

Cataloguing/Archiving Site Content 2 (all other file types)

Include all files and digital objects to which you would like users to have access.

Please upload any data in spreadsheet format (.xls or .ods)

Please upload any project data in documentary (.txt) form.

Please upload any project data in image form (.jpg or TIFF).

Do you have more than 21 image files to upload?

Yes No

Please upload any project data in database format (DBF)

Please upload any project data in audio (.wav) or video (.avi) form.

Please upload any of the project's geospatial data (ESRI_shape)

Cataloguing/Archiving Site Content 3: How to create a WARC file using WebRecorder

WebRecorder is an open source web recording tool that create high-fidelity, interactive recordings of any web site that is browsed with the tool. It allows for scholars to create a stable .warc file that can be replayed offline using the free webrecorder player. WebRecorder also allows users to create a collection of archived web-content that can be viewed online. The intent of web recording or archiving is to help scholars preserve the original output of their digital production whether it be an interactive map or a dynamic website, by capturing the dynamic content without modification and giving users a way of recreating the experience of browsing through the digital project. This Archiving wizard uses the WebRecorder archive service as part of the DDP, but there are other free open source tool for creating stable .warc file. Watch the following video tutorial to learn how to do a web recording of your project, or go to the resources page of the DDP: <https://digitalhumanitiesddp.com/resources/>

[WebRecorder Tutorial](#)

If you are able to create a web recording, upload the file (WARC) here

primera-navegación-20211121162643.warc

Cataloguing/Archiving Site Content 4: How to create a site diagram

There are many free online programs that allow you to create a map of your website. [One is here](#), but many others exist.

Untitled

Please upload a sitemap in pdf format.

Diagrama del Sitio.pdf

This will allow your users to understand where the archived files resided in your site architecture. If you would like, you may also include links to the archived files on your site map.

II.3. Creating Citable Project Documentation: The Archiving Dossier Narrative

The goal of the Archiving Dossier Narrative is to communicate the goals and successes of the project to both digitally and non-digitally oriented scholars. Ideally, the Archiving Dossier Narrative could then be published in field-specific journals to explain how the project corresponds to current scholarly work. Answer following questions and submit them; the answers will be collated by the cataloguer and a first draft of the narrative sent back for editing. The final version of the Archiving Dossier Narrative should be uploaded in Part 2 of the Archiving Wizard.

Have previous editions of this project already been archived?

Yes No

This is only for archived versions of completed projects. See the Best Practices page for further guidance

<https://wordpress.com/page/digitalhumanitiesddp.com/288>.

Please provide the DOI or URL for earlier editions of this project.

<https://zenodo.org/badge/DOI/10.5281/zenodo.5057910.svg>

See DDP Best Practices for clarification.

<https://wordpress.com/page/digitalhumanitiesddp.com/288>

Narrative Section 1: Project Rationale and Scope

El objetivo primordial del Repositorio es en compartir el Patrimonio Cultural de una mujer mexicana de finales del siglo XIX y principios del siglo XX, que ofrece un pensamiento nuevo y revolucionario expresado en la doctrina religiosa de la Espiritualidad de la Cruz, la cual consiste en abrazar la vida, la historia personal y transformar el dolor y la dificultad en amor.

Quizá esto último en la actualidad no es tan nuevo, ya que ciencias como la psicología contribuyen con el desarrollo humano y personal del individuo para su crecimiento y aceptación personal, sin embargo, en un México del siglo XIX en el que el trabajo interpersonal no era importante, Concepción Cabrera ofreció con su doctrina una alternativa que ayudó y tradujo una experiencia espiritual y mística en un método de resiliencia que dejó en sus escritos y Cuenta de Conciencia para la actualidad.

Por medio de este proyecto que surge desde la interdisciplinariedad de las Humanidades Digitales se busca la recuperación, preservación y difusión de los manuscritos más importantes de Concepción Cabrera, en el que a su vez se comparte su doctrina y, por otro lado, se salvaguarda todo su legado utilizando las herramientas digitales que ofrecen en la actualidad las distintas tecnologías.

Explain the rationale and scope of the project, with an emphasis on how the project corresponds to current scholarship. The answer should be approximately 1-2 pages in length.

Narrative Section 2: Project Trajectory

a) Definición del proyecto digital:

Utilicé como referencia para la elaboración del proyecto de investigación el libro: Diseño de proyectos sociales: aplicaciones prácticas para su planificación, gestión y evaluación, Pérez (2016) (Qué se quiere hacer, para qué, cuánto, cómo, dónde y con qué recursos humanos y económicos se llevará a cabo el proyecto) y las herramientas que presenta la Gestión de proyectos de Business Review, (2012). (Planificación, desarrollo y finalización evaluativa). A Través de estos dos métodos para los proyectos fue como empecé a sistematizar y documentar el proyecto.

b) Se creó una carpeta en Google Drive, con la finalidad de empezar a documentar las entrevistas, fotografías, videos etc.

c) Necesidades y usuarios:

Se inició con una investigación de campo, en el que se entrevistó a personas que viven y conocen la propuesta de Concepción Cabrera, es decir que tienen conocimientos básicos sobre la Espiritualidad de la Cruz y se les preguntó: cuando quieres encontrar información de la doctrina de la Beata, ¿en dónde buscas o cómo obtienes información?, el 80% de los entrevistados señalaron que no sabían dónde buscar y si lo hacían era en internet, pero la primer fuente de información era Wikipedia por lo cual lo consideraban muy básico. El otro 20% consultaba en libros o artículos de revistas impresos.

Lo anterior confirmó el inicio y la factibilidad del proyecto del Repositorio con la siguiente pregunta: ¿consideras necesario un repositorio digital en el que encuentres material e información sobre la doctrina de Concepción Cabrera? La respuesta fue: sí.

Describe the steps in the project. Among other project phases, please include information on project development, data collection and visualization, launch dates, project maintenance tasks, and the decision to archive, if applicable.

Narrative Section 3: Project-Specific Digital Objects and User Interface(s)

Se tienen como objetos digitalizados los manuscritos más importantes de la obra de Concepción Cabrera

Describe the digital objects created in the service of the project (eg. websites, spreadsheets, audio recordings, databases) and the tools used to create them. Please be specific about which versions of the tools were used (i.e., Omeka 2.0, Excel 2016, FileMaker Pro 15, etc.).

Narrative Section 4: Project Outcomes to Date (including analytics if possible)

Los resultados hasta hoy en un trabajo de análisis y distribución del patrimonio Cultural de una mujer Mexicana

If possible, provide a screenshot of the project's analytics and an explanation of any spikes in user activity. List any traditional scholarly products (articles, conference presentations, symposia, etc.) which resulted from this project.

Narrative Section 5. Documentation Statement

El objetivo es compartir la metodología y el proyecto para que más personas puedan conocer y así ver que sí es posible llevar a cabo la digitalización y recuperación del patrimonio cultural de tantas personas.

Explain the motivations for digitally documenting the project, whether for archival, re-evaluation, or other purposes. Provide a statement concerning the project's copyright status, and the conditions under which the project's assets are stored with the digital repository.

Narrative Section 6: Project Bibliography

Design & thinking - a documentary on design thinking [Video file]. (n.d.). Retrieved February 22, 2021.

<https://itesm.kanopy.com/video/design-and-thinking>

Brown, T. (2008). Design thinking. Harvard business review, 86(6), 84.

<https://readings.design/PDF/Tim%20Brown,%20Design%20Thinking.pdf>

Business Review, H. (2012). Gestión de proyectos. USA:Editorial . Reverté. Capítulo 1 pp. 3-19;

Capítulo 2 pp. 33-40, Capítulo 4 pp. 43-53. Recuperado de [https://0-elibro-net.biblioteca-](https://0-elibro-net.biblioteca-ils.tec.mx/es/lc/consorcioitesm/titulos/46768)

[ils.tec.mx/es/lc/consorcioitesm/titulos/46768](https://0-elibro-net.biblioteca-ils.tec.mx/es/lc/consorcioitesm/titulos/46768)Enlaces a un sitio externo.

Cantamutto, L., Rio Riande, G. y Striker, G. (2015). Las Humanidades Digitales desde Argentina:

Tecnología, Cultura, Saberes. Buenos Aires, Argentina: Editorial de la Facultad de Filosofía y Letras

Universidad de Buenos Aires. Recuperado de <http://repositorio.filo.uba.ar/handle/filodigital/1837>

Cohen, A. (2015). Chapter 1: The 11 deadly sins of product development. En Prototype to product: a practical guide for getting to market. O'Reilly Media, Inc.

Pérez Serrano, G. (2016). Diseño de Proyectos Sociales: Aplicaciones prácticas para su planificación,

gestión y evaluación. España: Narcea Ediciones. Capítulos 2 y 3. Recuperado de [https://0-elibro-](https://0-elibro-net.biblioteca-ils.tec.mx/es/lc/consorcioitesm/titulos/46246)

[net.biblioteca-ils.tec.mx/es/lc/consorcioitesm/titulos/46246](https://0-elibro-net.biblioteca-ils.tec.mx/es/lc/consorcioitesm/titulos/46246)Enlaces a un sitio externo.

The newberry. (2020). Renacimiento francés y paleografía. 5 de marzo de 2021, de Chicago's

independent research library Sitio web: <https://paleography.library.utoronto.ca/>

Please provide a project bibliography. If a bibliography is included in the project's webpages, a link to the archived pdf may be entered instead.

III. Storing Digital Project Assets (unpublished)

These documents are not for public view, nor for future citation, but can be used to track the history of the project and/or for future internal use.

Please upload any unpublished data in spreadsheet format for long term storage (.csv or .ods)

Please upload any unpublished project data in documentary (.txt) form for long term storage.

Please upload any unpublished project data in image form (.jpg or TIFF) for long term storage.

Please upload any project data in database format (DBF)

Please upload any project data in audio (.wav) or video (.avi) form.

Please upload any of the project's geospatial data (ESRI_shape)

Cataloguing/archiving next steps

Thank you for using the Archiving Wizard to catalogue your digital work. Please use the information you have collected to create your catalogue record and persistent identifier in the digital repository. Consult the [ddp self-archiving page](#) for the next steps in the process, or contact the cataloguer if you are archiving at an institution.